

MEDICAL SCIENCES

NEPHROPROTECTIVE PROPERTIES OF SULODEXIDE IN CORONARY HEART DISEASE PATIENTS WITH A HISTORY OF MYOCARDIAL REVASCULARIZATION

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Abstract

The aim of our study is to study the nephroprotective effect of sulodexide in patients with CHD who have undergone myocardial revascularization.

Results. 70 CHD patients with a history of myocardial revascularization were examined. Group I (n=36) - without DM, group II (n=34) - with DM. The control group (CG) consisted of 20 practically healthy individuals. All patients were prescribed the drug sulodexide at a dose of 500LE/day divided into 2 doses for 6 months.

After 6 months of sulodexide treatment, group I patients showed significant improvement in PSV at right ILA, left MRA, left ILA, RRI at the level of right SA, left MRA, left ILA. When laboratory parameters were studied after 6 months of sulodexide treatment, creatinine decreased to a greater extent in patients with DM from $114.44 \pm 6.84 \mu\text{mol/L}$ to $100.17 \pm 5.18 \mu\text{mol/L}$ compared to the values of the group of CHD patients without type 2 DM.

Conclusions. In patients without DM after treatment with sulodexide there were more significant positive changes in renal blood flow, especially at the level of smaller caliber arteries, which were more changed at the level of renal arteries on the left side in both groups.

Keywords: chronic kidney disease, sulodexide, renal artery duplex scanning, ischemic heart disease, cardio-renal syndrome

Background.

Cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of morbidity and mortality in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD). As the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) decreases, the likelihood of coronary heart disease (CHD) increases linearly, and patients with $\text{GFR} < 60 \text{ mL/min/1.73 m}^2$ have a 2- to 3-fold increased risk of mortality from CHD compared to patients without CKD [1].

CKD is defined as a change in renal function and structure for more than three months [2]. Currently, CKD represents a major global public health problem and is one of the leading causes of death worldwide [3]. It is still a challenge to identify prognostic markers of CKD and to assess whether these markers are independently associated with disease outcome.

Ultrasound Doppler scanning is one of the most accessible, noninvasive and informative methods of diagnostics of renal hemodynamic disorders [4]. According to the work of Popel O.N. and co-authors, ultrasound duplex scanning of renal vessels should be performed as an assessment of early renal damage in patients with CHD. The work recommends determination of renal resistive index (RRI) not only in the segmental artery, but also in the arc, interlobular and middle segment of the renal artery orifice to diagnose early renal damage [5].

Radjabova D. et al. studied renal hemodynamic disturbances in CHD patients with and without diabetes

mellitus (DM) [6]. This work demonstrated the importance of duplex scanning in early diagnosis and assessment of renal damage not only at the level of main renal arteries, but also at the level of segmental and interlobular renal arteries [6]. Despite all these studies emphasizing the prognostic role of RRI, physicians still do not use Doppler ultrasonography to assess the diagnosis and progression of CKD, as well as to evaluate the effectiveness of treatment with nephroprotective drugs.

Several studies have proven the nephroprotective role of sulodexide both in patients with and without the presence of DM [7, 15]. However, as an assessment of treatment efficacy, proteinuria indices as well as blood biochemical parameters were mainly studied. The study of the effect of sulodexide drug on the state of renal hemodynamics is poorly studied, therefore, in this study we would like to emphasize the study of this problem.

Methods.

Aim of the study to study the nephroprotective effect of sulodexide in patients with CHD who have undergone myocardial revascularization.

The study was conducted on the basis of "Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Therapy and Medical Rehabilitation" in the departments of cardiology, interventional cardiology and cardiac rehabilitation" (Tashkent, Uzbekistan). The control group consisted of 20 practically healthy individuals. The main group consisted of 70 patients with

stable angina pectoris FC I-III. All patients had undergone myocardial revascularization (percutaneous intervention (PCI) or coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG)) more than one year ago. Depending on the presence of diabetes mellitus, patients were categorized into 2 groups: Group I patients (n=36) without the presence of DM, Group II patients (n=34) with the presence of DM. When analyzing the initial clinical and laoboard parameters, both groups of patients were comparable in age, blood pressure (BP) level, body mass

index (BMI), GFR (Table 1). In spite of statistically insignificant changes in GFR indices in both groups, the stage of CHD in patients with diabetes corresponded to stage 3A, and in patients without diabetes to stage 2 of CKD (according to CKD-EPI classification). Significant differences were observed when comparing fasting blood glucose, glycated hemoglobin (HbA1) and blood creatinine levels (Table 1).

Table 1.

Clinical characteristics of the examined patients

Indicator	I group (without DM)	II group (with DM)	Control group
Age, years	65,49±1,05	65,86±1,24	42,37±2,64
BMI, kg/m ²	29,79±0,86	29,89±0,49	22,35±0,32*
Systolic BP, mmHg	138,16±25,35	138,27±6,26	118,41±5,22*
Dyastolic BP, mmHg	77,74±9,73	78,33±3,06	70,26±4,18*
HbA1, %	5,19±0,14	7,53±0,28^^	5,23±0,12
Fasting glycemia, mmol/l	5,22±0,12	8,79±0,53^^	5,02±0,15
Blood creatinine, μmol/l	99,27±5,29	114,44±6,85^	72,51±6,24**
GFR, ml/min/1,73m ²	64,13±3,61	59,14±4,08	93,21±5,72**

Note: difference between main group and CG:

* - p<0.05, ** - p<0.01; difference between I and II main groups: ^- p<0.05, ^^ - p<0.01.

All patients were prescribed sulodexide (Vessel du F, Catalent Italy, S.P.A. (Italy)) in oral form at a dose of 500LE/day divided into 2 doses for 6 months. Ultrasound duplex scanning of renal arteries, determination of creatinine level and GFR was performed in all patients before treatment and 6 months after treatment with sulodexide. In order to control the safety of sulodexide use, all patients after 1 and 3 months of treatment with the drug were evaluated for coagulogram parameters and platelet aggregation analysis. No cases of hemorrhagic complications were registered during the study.

Duplex scanning of renal arteries was performed on the ultrasound device "Philips Affinity 50G" (USA) with a 3.5 MHz C sensor in B-mode according to the generally accepted technique [9]. During the study, the peak systolic velocity (PSV, m/s), end-diastolic velocity (EDV, m/s), as well as renal resistive index (RRI, conventional units - c.u.) at the level of the main renal arteries (MRA), segmental arteries (SA) and interlobular arteries (ILA) on both sides were determined.

To determine the stage of CKD, we determined the GFR using the formula CKD-EPI (chronic kidney disease epidemiology collaboration, ml/min/1.73m²) according to the clinical guidelines 2020 [10].

Results.

When we compare baseline parameters of renal blood flow in patients with and without diabetes compared with the control group, there were observed significant deviations of all Doppler parameters at the

level of arteries of different caliber (starting with the main renal artery and ending with the interlobular arteries on both sides) (p<0.05, p<0.01). During duplex scanning of renal arteries, characteristic abnormalities in patients with CKD were increasing of RRI, PSV and decreasing of EDV in comparison with control group (p<0,05, p<0,01) (Table 2).

Analysis of baseline Doppler parameters revealed more pronounced changes in renal blood flow parameters at the level of all arteries in patients with diabetes, however, not all differences reached the threshold of reliability in comparison with patients without diabetes. The most significant and reliable deviations were observed at the level of lower caliber arteries, especially at the level of ILA on the right and SA on the left in favor of more significant deviations of renal blood flow parameters in group II patients (Table 2). At the level of the interlobular artery on the right, significant differences were observed regarding all renal blood flow parameters: PSV (47.06±2.4 m/s vs. 56.82±2.34 m/s, p<0.05), EDV (8.15±0.53 m/s vs. 11.25±0.6 m/s, p<0.05), RRI (0.68±0.02 vs. 0.73±0.02, p<0.05). At the level of the segmental artery on the left side, the same significant deviations were noted in all Dopplerographic parameters: PSV (39.1±3.44m/s vs. 50.96±4.97m/s, p<0.05), EDV (12.17±1.05m/s vs. 8.29±0.55m/s, p<0.05), RRI (0.70±0.02 vs. 0.75±0.01, p<0.05) (Table 2).

Renal parameters in the examined patients before treatment

Artery	Indicator	I group (without DM)	II group (with DM)	Control group
Right MRA	PSV, m/s	66,24±5,29	63,78±4,36	56,52±2,43°
	EDV, m/s	14,16±1,25	11,35±0,89	19,52±1,08°
	RRI, c.u.	0,72±0,016	0,73±0,02	0,67±0,016°
Right SA	PSV, m/s	46,4±3,88	49,09±3,91	40,72±2,67°
	EDV, m/s	10,51±0,80	9,49±0,56	17,32±0,72°°
	RRI, c.u.	0,71±0,016	0,72±0,02	0,66±0,014°
Right ILA	PSV, m/s	47,06±2,4	56,82±3,34*	35,8±2,67°°
	EDV, m/s	8,15±0,53	11,25±0,6*	15,35±0,51°
	RRI, c.u.	0,68±0,02	0,73±0,02*	0,65±0,012
Left MRA	PSV, m/s	64,99±5,99	66,53±5,12	55,48±3,27°
	EDV, m/s	14,02±2,65	13,73±1,72	18,35±1,12°
	RRI, c.u.	0,74±0,02	0,75±0,022	0,68±0,012°°
Left SA	PSV, m/s	39,1±3,44	50,96±4,97*	41,61±3,33°
	EDV, m/s	12,17±1,05	8,29±0,55*	16,22±0,85°
	RRI, c.u.	0,70±0,02	0,75±0,01*	0,65±0,013°
Left ILA	PSV, m/s	57,60±7,3	53,32±6,17	37,67±2,83°
	EDV, m/s	8,15±0,74	7,49±0,86	14,73±0,68°°
	RRI, c.u.	0,71±0,03	0,70±0,019	0,65±0,013°
	Blood creatinine, μmol/l	99,27±5,29	114,44±6,84*	72,51±6,24°°
	GFR, ml/min/1,73m ²	64,13±3,61	59,14±4,08	93,21±5,72°°

Note: difference of initial indicators between I and II main groups :

*- p<0.05, **- p<0.01; difference between main group and CG: °- p<0.05, °°- p<0.01;

The results of the studied parameters after a 6-month course of sulodexide treatment were analyzed. As can be seen from Table 3, in patients without DM after treatment with sulodexide there were more significant positive changes in renal blood flow, especially at the level of smaller caliber arteries. Moreover, we would like to note that the improvement of Doppler parameters was more recorded at the level of renal arteries on the left than on the right, both in patients with and without diabetes.

Group I patients showed significant improvement in PSV at the level of ILA on the right (from 47.06±2.4m/s to 35.62±3.66m/s, p<0.05), MRA on the left (from 64.99±5.99m/s to 56.55±4.26m/s, p<0.05), ILA on the left (from 57.60±7.3m/s to 34.12±2.75m/s, p<0.05), RRI at the level of SA on the right (c 0.71±0.016 to 0.67±0.014, p<0.05), MRA on the left (c 0.74±0.02 to 0.7±0.017, p<0.05), ILA on the left (c 0.71±0.03 to 0.65±0.01, p<0.05).

Table 3.

Renal parameters in CHD patients without DM after 6 months sulodexide treatment			
Artery	Indicator	Before treatment	6 months after treatment
Right MRA	PSV, m/s	66,24±5,29	60,27±3,92
	EDV, m/s	14,16±1,25	12,56±1,03
	RRI, c.u.	0,72±0,016	0,70±0,012
Right SA	PSV, m/s	46,4±3,88	42,88±3,84
	EDV, m/s	10,51±0,80	12,55±0,82
	RRI, c.u.	0,71±0,016	0,67±0,014*
Right ILA	PSV, m/s	47,06±2,4	35,62±3,66*
	EDV, m/s	8,15±0,53	9,97±0,60
	RRI, c.u.	0,68±0,02	0,65±0,014
Left MRA	PSV, m/s	64,99±5,99	56,55±4,26*
	EDV, m/s	14,02±2,65	15,46±0,93
	RRI, c.u.	0,74±0,02	0,7±0,017*
Left SA	PSV, m/s	39,1±3,44	38,71±3,59
	EDV, m/s	12,17±1,05	11,45±0,71
	RRI, c.u.	0,70±0,02	0,67±0,012
Left ILA	PSV, m/s	57,60±7,3	34,12±2,75**
	EDV, m/s	8,15±0,74	10,82±0,74
	RRI, c.u.	0,71±0,03	0,65±0,01*
	Blood creatinine, $\mu\text{mol/l}$	99,27±5,29	89,18±4,22
	GFR, ml/min/1,73M ²	64,13±3,61	67,85±3,12

Note: difference of indicators before and after treatment: *- $p < 0.05$, ** - $p < 0.01$

In patients with DM, significant improvement of renal blood flow was observed only at the level of MRA on the left and ILA on the left: PSV at the level of ILA on the left (from $53.32 \pm 6.17 \text{ m/s}$ to $41.16 \pm 3.041 \text{ m/s}$, $p < 0.05$), EDV at the level of ILA on the left (from $13.73 \pm 1.72 \text{ m/s}$ to $9.23 \pm 0.7 \text{ m/s}$, $p < 0.05$), RRI at the level of ILA on the left (from 0.70 ± 0.019 to

0.66 ± 0.015) (Table 4). As can be seen from the above, the improvement of renal blood flow in patients with DM was noted only at the level of 2 arteries, in contrast to patients without DM, in whom the improvement of Doppler parameters was recorded at the level of 4 arteries.

Renal parameters in CHD patients with DM after 6 months sulodexide treatment

Artery	Indicator	Before treatment	6 months after treatment
Right MRA	PSV, m/s	63,78±4,36	59,52±4,91
	EDV, m/s	11,35±0,89	12,81±0,95
	RRI, c.u.	0,73±0,02	0,71±0,015
Right SA	PSV, m/s	49,09±3,91	43,40±3,22
	EDV, m/s	9,49±0,56	10,66±0,43
	RRI, c.u.	0,72±0,02	0,7±0,012
Right ILA	PSV, m/s	56,82±3,34	48,25±3,21
	EDV, m/s	11,25±0,6	12,57±0,44
	RRI, c.u.	0,73±0,02	0,7±0,013
Left MRA	PSV, m/s	66,53±5,12	57,23±3,93
	EDV, m/s	13,73±1,72	14,23±0,7
	RRI, c.u.	0,75±0,022	0,72±0,018
Left SA	PSV, m/s	50,96±4,97	49,1±4,51
	EDV, m/s	8,29±0,55	8,73±0,82
	RRI, c.u.	0,75±0,01	0,72±0,014
Left ILA	PSV, m/s	53,32±6,17	41,16±3,041*
	EDV, m/s	7,49±0,86	9,3±0,45
	RRI, c.u.	0,70±0,019	0,66±0,015*
	Blood creatinine, $\mu\text{mol/l}$	114,44±6,84*	100,17±5,18*
	GFR, ml/min/1,73M ²	59,14±4,08	63,34±4,05

Note: difference of indicators before and after treatment: *- $p < 0.05$

Based on the above mentioned, RRI and PSV were the indicators that reflected the improvement of renal blood flow.

At studying laboratory parameters after 6-month course of sulodexide treatment creatinine decreased to a greater extent in patients with DM from $114,44 \pm 6,84 \mu\text{mol/l}$ to $100,17 \pm 5,18 \mu\text{mol/l}$ ($p < 0,05$) in comparison with parameters of the group of CHD patients without type 2 DM. Increase in GFR was observed in both groups, but intergroup differences did not reach the threshold of reliability ($p > 0.05$).

Discussion.

Sulodexide is a combination drug composed of fast-acting heparin and dermatansulfate, which can prevent the degradation of heparin sulfate and restore the ion-selective permeability of glomerular basement membrane to a certain extent. It has potential significance for the comprehensive treatment of proteinuria [11].

Previous studies have shown that sulodexide has a significant effect on reducing albumin excretion rate in patients with diabetes mellitus [12]. Long-term administration of low-dose sulodexide has antiproteinuric and nephroprotective effects in patients with CKD caused

by diabetic nephropathy, primary glomerulonephritis and hypertensive nephropathy. In these cases, sulodexide plays an important role in protecting renal function and delaying the progression of renal disease to a certain extent [13].

Novikova M.S. et al. conducted a meta-analysis of treatment of patients with diabetic nephropathy with glycosaminoglycans (in particular, sulodexide), where, in general, sulodexide therapy was accompanied by a significant decrease in protein excretion with urine [14]. The data obtained indicate the renoprotective effect of sulodexide in diabetic patients with albuminuria and may serve as a basis for the treatment of diabetic nephropathy with sulodexide, in particular for the prevention of end-stage renal disease associated with DM [14].

Also, Angelo A Bignamini et al. conducted a systematic review and meta-analysis of the treatment of complications of type 2 DM with sulodexide [15]. The findings of this review indicate the positive effects of sulodexide on peripheral arteries, lower extremity venous system, and the efficacy of treatment of diabetic nephropathy. The review details the different treatment

regimens of sulodexide and suggests a treatment regimen of 500LE/day [15].

The change in blood flow velocity assessed by Doppler ultrasonography allows the RRI to be calculated [16]. Initially, RRI was used to assess arterial stiffness. The normal RRI in an adult ranges between 0.47 and 0.7, and the difference between the two kidneys should not exceed 5-8% [17]. Thus, any factors that decrease vascular resistance and increase pulse pressure causes an increase in RRI, such as advanced age, smoking, hypertension, atherosclerosis and CKD.

Many studies have been conducted on the positive effect of glycosaminoglycans on the kidney, but the effect of this group of drugs on renal blood flow has not been studied. We would also like to note that there are many works, where the study includes mainly patients with CHD with the presence of diabetes, but very few works devoted to the study of nephroprotective effect of sulodexide in patients with CHD without the presence of type 2 diabetes.

In this study we demonstrated the effectiveness of sulodexide treatment in CHD patients with the presence of CKD. In addition, renal blood flow indices reflecting the presence of CKD were determined.

Conclusions.

1. When comparing baseline parameters of renal blood flow in patients with and without CKD in comparison with the control group were observed significant deviations of all Doppler parameters at the level of arteries of different caliber, starting from the main renal artery and ending with the interlobular arteries on both sides.

2. In patients with CHD at duplex scanning of renal arteries characteristic abnormalities of CKD were increasing of RRI, PSV and decreasing of EDV in comparison with the control group.

3. When analyzing baseline Doppler parameters, more pronounced changes in renal blood flow parameters at the level of ILA on the right and SA on the left were revealed in favor of more significant deviations of renal blood flow parameters in patients with the presence of DM.

4. In CHD patients without DM after sulodexide treatment more significant positive changes in renal blood flow were observed especially at the level of smaller caliber arteries.

5. Improvement of renal blood flow in patients with DM was noted only at the level of MRA and ILA on the left, in contrast to patients without DM, in whom improvement of Doppler parameters was determined at the level of ILA on the right and left, MRA on the left, SA on the right, ILA on the left.

6. After 6-month course of sulodexide treatment creatinine decreased to a greater extent in patients with DM from $114,44 \pm 6,84 \mu\text{mol/l}$ to $100,17 \pm 5,18 \mu\text{mol/l}$ ($p < 0,05$) in comparison with the group of CHD patients without type 2 DM (from $99,27 \pm 5,29$ to $89,18 \pm 4,22$, $p > 0,05$).

List of abbreviations

BMI – body mass index

BP – blood pressure

CABG – coronary artery bypass grafting

CG – control group

CHD – coronary heart disease

CKD – chronic kidney disease

DM – diabetes mellitus

EDV – end-dyastolic velocity

GFR – glomerular filtration rate

HbA1 - glycated hemoglobin

ILA – interlobular artery

MRA – main renal artery

PCI – percutaneous intervention

PSV – peak systolic velocity

RRI – renal resistive index

SA – segmental artery

Declarations.

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Informed consent was obtained from all patients who entered this study. Meanwhile, informed written consent has been obtained from the participants who participated in the study.

Consent for publication

All authors gave consent for publication the research.

Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Authors' contributions.

Research concept and design – Alyavi A., Radjabova D.; collection of material - Radjabova D., Yakubov M.; statistical processing of data, analysis and interpretation of results, writing the text - Radjabova D., Tulyaganova D., Khan T.; editing - Alyavi A., Radjabova D. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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